

GENERALIZING AND DIFFERENTIATING ASPECTS OF ARTISTIC ARTS

Ibrohimova Gulkhayo Utkir kizi

Student

Department of foreign philology,
Bukhara State University

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8033114>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 04th June 2023

Accepted: 12th June 2023

Online: 13th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Development of certain types, art, temporal view includes theater.

ABSTRACT

Artistic culture is a complex system in which art forms play an important role. This is a product of a long historical development, and in ancient times it was not divided into areas of artistic activity - types. Types of art: literature, architecture, sculpture, music, visual arts, etc. The first direction of the sources of aesthetic thinking is the complexity, diversity, versatility of reality. The second direction is the connection with the wealth of human emotions, perceptual features, and human spiritual abilities. Art types cannot substitute for each other: each of them is independent, extremely rare and unique, directly reflects one aspect of reality, this or that type takes priority over other types in expressing human qualities and emotions, and has certain limited features.

The celebration of social justice or the increase of conflicts in society, the violation of equality and harmony affects the development of art, the development of certain types, that is, "unevenness" occurs. For example, during the Islamic Renaissance, all types of art, especially poetry, fine art, music, and architecture, developed widely because Islam opened the way to social justice.

During the practice of art, its two characteristics - the tendency to separation and concentration - are clearly visible. If the art of separation is related to the emergence of new types, their striving for independence, the art of integration is seen in the striving of some kind of competition. Today, concentration can encompass the entire culture as a whole.

Categorization is an important tool for knowing and studying art. Now, it has become a trend to study art with spatial, temporal, spatial-temporal views. Visual art, sculpture, line drawing (graphics), applied art and architecture are considered to be fine. The temporal view includes fiction and music, and the spatial - temporal view includes theater, cinema, and the world of mirrors. There is a connection and dependence between these two foundations.

While art is an independent sphere of social life, it is also closely related to non-artistic spheres of human activity.

Among the types of art, fiction takes a special place. Literary literature appears as a water orca. It is called water art. Word art has two forms: oral and written. The art of water first appeared in oral form. Oral literature is active in the life of a number of peoples in the form of folk tales and folk tales, and secondly, it is active in performing arts and forms of communication, and belongs to all peoples of the world. In oral literature, water and performer are common. In one moment, the author and the performer become one.

The main material tool, pictorial and expressive means of written literature is water. A word is an expression of an idea, a statement of an idea, and through words, people's cognitive activities fall on paper and become embedded in the brain. Thanks to words, the intellectual wealth accumulated by mankind reaches future generations. The word is the most important component of human culture, and through it, written literature, which has acquired a material and spiritual form, has become an intellectual form of art. The material and spiritual world, the mental and spiritual world of a person is most profoundly and comprehensively reflected in written literature. Written literature differs from other forms of art in its intellectual activity, i.e., creation and performance at once, even without special preparation or semi-preparation.

The difference between oral and written literature is manifested in their different effects on human emotions. Apart from the fact that it is intended for hearing the spoken word, seeing and reading what is written, the comprehension of written literature requires more creative activity and independence from the reader, comparing the information obtained from the literary text with his own spiritual world and life experience.

In the history of the artistic culture of ancient Greece, the scope of fiction included its three major literary genres - epic, lyrical, and dramatic. The epic type was used, first of all, with the artistic continuation of the events, the lyrical type - with the mood and mental state, and the dramatic type - with the movement. All the signs of these three types were closely related to reality, which was necessary for artistic reflection.

The types of fiction, in turn, are divided into several types and forms. They are folk epic, epic epic, epic novel, novel, short story; lyrical type - kasida, tuyuk, rubai, ghazal, mustakhzad, poem; in dramatic form - tragedy (tragedy), comedy, drama, etc.

Painting, sculpture, line drawing (graphics) belong to the system of visual arts, and their creation dates back to the most ancient times of human history. The artists of the ancient world created symbols that corresponded to their interests and needs. The animals depicted in the paintings took the place of real events and scenes of life. Fine art was freed from the dominance of such useful and practical purposes and turned into a specialized form of artistic activity, and this process lasted for many centuries. Different types of visual arts differ from each other - each of them reflects the reality scene in its own way, but in the end they merge into one system. The means of expression of painting, sculpture and line drawing are diverse, and the boundaries between the depicted and represented things are conditional and relative. The artist reproduces the material world in his creative imagination and depicts it on a plane. In the painting, autumn colors are reflected using a unique art "language" - color. In it, the visible color of the world is reflected with sensitivity and freedom. Light-shadow is widely used in painting, it is an integral part of painting. Rembrandt, the great Dutch painter in European visual arts.

The system of performing arts includes theater, open stage (variety), circus, cinema, television. These fields are united by the house together with the diversity.

Theater art has spatial and temporal characteristics. The object in it - the atmosphere of the equipment, stage decorations, clothing and finally the character of the actor has a certain spatial character. Actor's skill is a fundamental and rare feature of theater art. An actor can be a creator, a dresser, and a performer at the same time on the stage. The word "theatre" is derived from the Greek word "tetron", and the ancient Greeks called the places where public performances were held "theatron". European researchers build the foundations of these spectacles in the Dionysian rites. The unique "language" of the theater is character. Theater art is a type of collective art, the achievement of which is manifested in the achievement of artistic integrity.

Open stage and circus art are close to theater art. The inner emotional-emotional content of the open stage program comes from the task of opening the house - laughter or entertainment. The art of the circus is a combination of performing skills on various devices, clowning, acrobatics and animal training. These require dexterity from a circus performer. The basis of this art is the theme of the queue (number). Circus performances combine various art forms.

Cinema art is one of the forms of manifestation of cinematographic technique. Its technical basis is photography and film camera. Other types of cinematographic art, types, views are derived from the means of expression. Contemporary cinematography comes into existence with a number of means of expression. Color is gaining more and more importance in it. Cinema is alive with sound. Sound cinema expands the possibilities of human cognition. The movie has its own requirements for the movie actor. The first artistic task of television was to show the effects of art types, types, and performances. Now he has decided to pursue aesthetic work as a separate field

Almost all types of art and styles are absorbed into the "Mirror World" bar and become an effective means of aesthetic impact.

The concept of genre is appropriately defined by various concepts of art, and the aesthetic attitude of a person to reality is manifested in a generalized form. The concept of genre comes from the need to categorize art, that is, it shows the commonality of some kind of artistic phenomena. The genre is theoretical today, from which the world of artistic works begins. The content of the genre also expresses the specific meaning of the type, type, appearance. For example, the tragedy genre reflects the tragic conflicts and aspects of life, and it also expresses the manifestation of life conflicts in human will, aspirations, and beliefs. Art types have their common genre features. For example, in painting, domestic, historical, and scenic themes give rise to genre views. Genre is a socio-historical concept, the processes of its development and change, the emergence of one and the other, depend on social factors outside the sphere of pure art. At the same time, the genre also shows the independence of art development. The renewal of genres, the emergence of new ones is a symbolic expression of the power of art, a guarantee of its vital and symbolic meaning. This point has been shown in the works of great artists, and this tradition continues today.

References:

1. Бекчанова, С. (2023). СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА ЛИЧНОСТЬЮ СКВОЗЬ ПРИЗМУ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И КУЛЬТУРНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(4 Part 4), 32–36. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/13213> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867146>.
2. Бекчанова Солиха Давлатназаровна. (2022). ШАХСНИНГ КАСБГА БЎЛГАН ҚИЗИҚИШИ, ЛАЁҚАТИ ВА ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРИНИ АМАЛИЙ ЎРГАНИШДА ЖАҲОН ТАЖРИБАСИ. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2(12), 774–780. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353435>.
3. Бекчанова Солиха Давлатназаровна. (2022). ОСНОВНЫЕ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩИЕ ПРАВСТВЕННОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКА. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6483370>. *The possibilities of using textbooks during mother tongue classes*
4. Т Ozoda.ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 5 (5), 408-418
5. Tursunova Ozoda . On the use of study dictionaries in mother language lessons of general secondary schools //EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH//14-19
6. Principles of creating the "annotated dictionary of paronyms" for secondary school students O.F. Tursunova 2022/10/22 //Eurasian journal of social sciences, philosophy and culture//2/216-223
7. [High human feelings in Rudakis work.](#)// Theoretical & Applied Science/986-99
8. Tursunova, O. (2023). ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS DURING THE LESSONS OF RUSSIAN AS A NATIVE LANGUAGE, INCLUDING THE STUDY OF LEXICAL COMPOSITION BASED ON LEXICOGRAPHIC METHODS, IN PARTICULAR, THE SPECIFICS OF PARONYMS. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана, 1(4), 93–96. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yopa/article/view/12287>.
9. Зикиряева , М. . (2023). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛОГИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ БУДУЩИХ ВРАЧЕЙ. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(3 Part 2), 159–164. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11207> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7736831>
10. [О методологии психологического образования.](#) А.А Ахмедов, М.М Зикиряева.Вестник интегративной психологии 19 (79), 63-67, 2019/9/3
11. [Психологические особенности взаимоотношений мальчиков и девочек в младших классах.](#) Зикиряева М.М. (г. Бухара, Узбекистан) Вестник 24/2022 128-130с
12. [Бошланғич синф ўқитувчисининг ўзига хос психологик хусусиятлари.](#) “Journal of new century innovations” international interdisciplinary research journal. 05.05.2022. 244-249 б.
13. [Psychology in teaching english language.](#) “Eurasian journal of social sciences, philosophy and culture”. Ziki ryayeva Manzura Mavlonovna, Hakimova Muhabbat Alimovna, Volume 2 Issue 5, May 2022. ISSN 2181-2888. 228-232 p.

14. [Тиббиёт олий таълим муассасалари талабаларини мантикий тафаккурини ривожлантиришнинг психологик механизмлари](#). Зикиряева М.М. Journal of new century innovations. 2022.11.07,16(3), 33–39 p.
15. [Олий таълим муассасалари талабаларида креативликни шакллантириш](#). Зикиряева М.М. Eurasian journal of academic research. 2022.10.19. 926-931 p.
16. [Психологические механизмы формирования социального воображения у подростков](#). А.А Ахмедов, М.М Зикиряева. Тиббиётда янги кун. 151-154 стр, 1(29)2020
17. [Madaniyatlararo tafovutlarning glaballashuv sharoitida ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlar](#). М.М Zikiryaeva. Таълим ва ривожланиш таҳлили онлайн илмий журнали 2 (3), 240-245, 2022/5/5
18. [SHaxs psixologiyasida ranglarning egallagan o'rni xususida](#). М.М Zikiryaeva. Тафаккур ва талқин, 475-485, 2020/5/15
19. [Ўсмирлар хулқ-атворида ижтимоий қадриятлар шаклланишига таъсир этувчи омилларни методологик асослари](#). М.М Зикиряева, Psixologiya 4 (4), 124-128, 4/2020
20. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). INTRA-LINGUISTIC AND EXTRA-LINGUISTIC FACTORS RELATED TO THE LANGUAGE AND VOCABULARY OF THE BASIC CONCEPTS OF RENAISSANCE ENGLISH PHILOSOPHY. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 1(5), 9-17.
21. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(5), 990-995.
22. Мирзаева, А. Ш. (2021). РЕМИНИСЦЕНЦИЯ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ ИНТЕРТЕКСТУАЛЬНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ РИКА РИОРДАНА "PERCY JACKSON AND THE LIGHTNING THIEF". *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(3).
23. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). THEORY IN INTERTEXTUALITY AND THREE SEAMLESS INTERTEXTS: M. BUTTERFLY BY DAVID H. HWANG, AS IS BY WILLIAM M. HOFFMAN, AND EXECUTION OF JUSTICE BY EMILY MANN. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(5-2), 160-165.
24. Shavkatovna, M. A. (2022). ENLIGHTENMENT-MORAL, PHILOSOPHICAL, LINGUISTIC VIEWS OF MODERN CREATORS.
25. Shavkatovna, M. A. . (2022). Interrextuality in Rick Riordan's Work. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(9), 180–185. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1507>.
26. Mirzaeva Aziza Shavkatovna. (2021). Allusion As The Way Of Rendering Elements Of Ancient Greek Mythology In The Tissue Of Modern Literature. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(01), 505-514. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume03Issue01-91>
27. Shavkatovna, M. A. . (2022). Interrextuality in Rick Riordan's Work. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(9), 180–185. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1507>
28. Aziza Mirzaeva Shavkatovna. (2022). THE INTERTEXTUAL AND INTERCULTURAL REFERENCES IN LODGE'S CAMPUS NOVELS. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 2(11), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue11-05>

29. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION.
30. Shahob Sharofitdinovich Shodiev. *Academicia An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* "Interpretation of philosophical terms and concepts as an essential subject for linguistic researches of XIX-XX centuries, held in Russia and Europe" 590-98 10.5958/2249-7137.2020.01171.4
31. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev. Bakaev Najmiddin Bakaevich. expressions.. (2020). The role of the Latin language in the history of world statehood. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 05 (85), 367-372. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-05-85-71> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> Scopus ASCC: 1203. THE ROLE OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN THE HISTORY OF WORLD STATEHOOD
32. Sh.Sh.Shodiyev. N.B.Bakayev. M.N.Khafizova, S.N.Ostonova " SHAKESPEARS LEXICON: REASON WORD AS A DESIGN OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ABILITY OF THE HUMAN MIND TO ABSTRACTION, CONCLUSION " *Theoretical and Applied Science*, 162-166, 2020
33. Ш.Ш. Шодиев, Д.Я.Шигабутдинова. «ШЕКСПИРОВСКИЙ ЛЕКSIKON: CЛОВО REASON KAK OBOZNAЧAHИE ПОНЯТИЯ СПOCOБHOCTИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО УМА К АБСТРАКЦИИ УМОЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЮ» *Инновационный потенциал развития науки в современном мире*, 189-197, 2020 General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language TN
34. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Majitova Nafisa Zokirovna. (2021). IDEAS ABOUT AN IDEAL PERSON, LANGUAGE, PROSPERITY IN THE EVOLUTION OF PUBLIC AND POLITICAL VIEWS OF THE UZBEK JADIDS OF THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 1(3), 5-8. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925897>
35. Шодиев Шахобиддин Шарофиддинович. (2022). "МАКБЕТ" ВА "АБУЛФАЙЗХОН" ТРАГЕДИЯСИДА ФАЛСАФИЙ СЎЗЛАР ВА NATURE /ТАБИАТ" ВА SOCIETY / ЖАМИЯТ ТУШУНЧАСИ. *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH*, 2(12), 1142-1150. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390238>
36. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev, Najmiddin Bakaevich Bakaev, Nafisa Zainiddinovna Tasheva *STUDYING PHILOSOPHICAL REALITIES OF THE RENAISSANCE EPOCH, BASED ON THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHILOSOPHICAL TEXTS // Academic research in educational sciences*. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/studying-philosophical-realities-of-the-renaissance-epoch-based-on-the-structural-analysis-of-philosophical-texts>.
37. Shahob Sharofitdinovich Shodiev. *Academicia An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* "Interpretation of philosophical terms and concepts as an essential subject for linguistic researches of XIX-XX centuries, held in Russia and Europe" 590-98 10.5958/2249-7137.2020.01171.4
38. Sh.Sh.Shodiyev. N.B.Bakayev. M.N.Khafizova, S.N.Ostonova " SHAKESPEARS LEXICON: REASON WORD AS A DESIGN OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ABILITY OF THE HUMAN MIND TO ABSTRACTION, CONCLUSION " *Theoretical and Applied Science*, 162-166, 2020
39. Ш.Ш. Шодиев, Д.Я.Шигабутдинова. «ШЕКСПИРОВСКИЙ ЛЕКSIKON: CЛОВО REASON KAK OBOZNAЧAHИE ПОНЯТИЯ СПOCOБHOCTИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО УМА К

АБСТРАКЦИИ УМОЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЮ» Инновационный потенциал развития науки в современном мире, 189-197, 2020

40. Shodiyev Shaxobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Tasheva Nafisa Zayniddinovna. (2021). THE ROLE OF THE WAY OF THE GREAT STEPPE IN THE CONTINUITY AND RELATIONSHIP OF THE PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE OF THE MUSLIM EAST AND THE RENAISSANCE WEST. Innovative Academy Research Support Center, 1(3), 9–13. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925956>

41. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Majitova Nafisa Zokirovna. (2021). IDEAS ABOUT AN IDEAL PERSON, LANGUAGE, PROSPERITY IN THE EVOLUTION OF PUBLIC AND POLITICAL VIEWS OF THE UZBEK JADIDS OF THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(3), 5–8. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925897>